

Meta-level Experience Sharing for Autonomous Systems by Fusing Generative Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks

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Abstract—Experience sharing is a fundamental learning capability of human nature. Imagine that you need to pass through a congested road in the shortest time possible. You would try to remember how you previously handle such situations and optimize the route by fusing this knowledge with previous similar experiences. In addition, one can integrate these experiences with other information sources that suggest solutions. Transferring this type of intelligence to autonomous navigation systems implies the ability to first represent experiences through discriminative and generative models, and then create new optimal models, by fusing new and existing scenarios that the agent encounters. We propose a meta-level experience-sharing and learning method for a Bayesian autonomous agent. We introduce a joint state estimation method for discrete and continuous random variables, using Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks. In the proposed system, meta-level knowledge is learned and represented from lower dimensional odometry data, by observing behaviors from a third-person viewpoint. The learned knowledge is then transformed into a first-person agent viewpoint to perform such tasks online. Multiple learned predictive models and new experiences are fused into a single and more robust model during the online stage. Through the principle of free energy minimization, the learned Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks are used to coherently estimate discrete and continuous state variables for hierarchical-level anomaly detection and inference problems. Our results demonstrate that the proposed method optimizes the number of models by fusing similar experiences managed by the agent, while making anomaly detection and incremental learning steps more robust.

Index Terms—Meta Clustering, Autonomous Experiences Sharing, Active Learning, Fusion of Bayesian generative models, World models for self-awareness

I. INTRODUCTION

Experience involves perception and action that can be termed as consciousness [1]. It refers to an active engagement with the environment that an agent interacts with. Each meaningful and continuous interaction with the environment

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becomes a shared (when also considering multi-agent systems [2]) or individual learning experience. This experience as meta-information (i.e., knowledge gained through experience, what to do with it, and how to reuse it) is an additional knowledge that is essential for a cognitive agent to have for learning purposes. This experience can be explored through dynamic Bayesian approaches to perform different tasks [3].

In sequential learning, mining sequential patterns from different experiences is the main objective of an agent. Each pattern can be stored in an autobiographical memory as a profile for further processes. Each interaction of an agent with the surrounding environment can be treated as an event. The collection of events can be ordered sequentially to form a sequence of events. A sequence can be grouped into meta-groups having similar characteristics. Considering an odometric trajectory (sequences of positional data) as an experience, sequential linear movements can be grouped together, while sequential curved movements can be grouped together as well. This type of clustering helps an agent to abstract the environment. When the agent invokes an event in a previously experienced environment, it exploits the meta-information stored in its autobiographical memory [4]–[7].

Clustering and cluster analysis involve multi-variate data described by a vector of attributes called features [8]. To cluster collected data, it is important to assess if some features are more relevant than others through further processes like filtering. After the computation of relevant features, to cluster this information, knowing the number of clusters is challenging. Domain knowledge or specific algorithms that are able to produce the optimal number of clusters are needed. Methods based on variance, such as principal component analysis or Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), need to consider not only good features (low variance) for clustering but to include the intrinsic behavior of the data as well (or relationships between data points) to produce the optimal number of clusters. Hence, guarantying optimality of the number of clusters is an ill-posed problem.

Clustering can be performed through filtering [5] or through clustering algorithms [9]. The filter-based approach depends

only on the dataset as an algorithm independent process [8]. This method assigns feature weights based on the consistency of the feature value among the n nearest neighbors of each data point. In this case, the mutual information between the relevant features of each data point and the cluster properties should be high. A feature can be grouped together if the cluster properties and its properties have common points. The algorithm-based approach, instead, evaluates the whole group of the data and, considering a specific criterion, classifies each data point into subsets (or clusters) having common properties [10]. Cluster separability can assess the methodology results by evaluating the quality of the clusters obtained.

Optimality in clustering methods must assess both Inter Cluster Similarity (ICS) and Inter Cluster Dissimilarity (ICD) [11]. ICS is a quality measure that can be used to reduce the number of clusters in a sequence. Distance measures are suitable for trajectory-based clusters. Here, noise and outliers may degrade cluster optimality. The Inter Cluster Validation [11] is determined based on cluster centroids. To minimize the effect of outliers and simplify re-clustering, hierarchical clustering methods are proposed in literature [12], [13].

Different clustering algorithms, like k -means [14], Self-Organizing Map (SOM) [15], Density-based spatial clustering (DBSCAN) [16], [17], Growing Neural Gas (GNG) [10], and Clique [18] algorithms can be used to group different features based on common feature attributes. When the domain knowledge is available, k -means and SOM can be used. In contrast, when the domain knowledge is not available, GNG and DBSCAN can be utilized to determine the number of clusters. All these clustering algorithms are not sequential in time though.

In this paper we propose a sequential clustering algorithm that builds clusters based on the free energy minimization principle [6]. We propose to hierarchically cluster temporal odometric data, after performing a filtering step on the odometry observations. The main contributions are: *i*) sequential clustering; *ii*) cluster optimization through comparative clustering; *iii*) experience fusion for similar learned models.

II. METHODOLOGY

The approach presented here is structured as described in Fig. 1. All the hierarchical sequential steps are based on a dynamic probabilistic representation that aligns with the free energy minimization principle. The final goal is to allow an agent to encode incrementally the observed experiences into generative models capable to predict data sequences compatible with the probabilistic rules learned by observing expert examples. In the following sections, the different steps are described in more detail by highlighting the main aspects.

A. Filtering

Experience modeling from the situational viewpoint can start by considering a noisy trajectory from an expert agent. Here, as an example, we consider noisy 2D odometric observations with positional information. The null force filter (see [19]) is used as a generalized filter that assumes an agent

to be in equilibrium in a condition where no force is present, i.e., a null acceleration implying null velocity. We can define a vector \mathcal{F}_t as:

$$\mathcal{F}_t = [x_t, y_t], \quad (1)$$

where x_t and y_t represent the position of an object in the x, y plane at a particular time t , acquired by the observer agent in a third-person reference system. The first goal of filtering (Step 1 in Fig. 1) is to obtain a set of probabilistic errors called generalized states (GSs) z_t describing how much the observed data sequence deviates from the null force assumption in each point. A Markov Jump Particle Filter [20] is used to this end. A GS z_t can be represented as a vector:

$$z_t = [x_t, y_t, v_{x_t}, v_{y_t}] = [zx_t, zv_t] \quad (2)$$

that is described considering the state changes v_{x_t} and v_{y_t} estimated with respect to the null force hypothesis at sparse points (x and y) collected during the agent's experience. In the odometry case, state changes correspond to the estimated speed caused by a local force not accounted for in the null force filter. This way, GS data form a temporal sequence that captures information about such local forces.

B. Clustering

Unsupervised clustering of GSs aims at learning a low complexity generative model (i.e., where parameters are minimized) capable to predict (also to synthesize) a new sequence of data \mathcal{F}_t following the same rules, i.e., based on the same set of forces that generated the expert realization.

A first level generative situation model (SM) is the objective of Step 1 in Fig. 1. Here, z_t is modeled as a random Gaussian process and the filtering process provides also the covariance matrix of each sample, so that z_t can be seen as a Gaussian random variable:

$$z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_t, C_t), \quad (3)$$

where $\mu_t \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the mean of the vector with dimension D , and $C_t \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ is the covariance matrix with dimension $D \times D$. The sequential unsupervised clustering approach of a single experience is structured into two distinct levels.

1) First Level Clustering: First level clustering (see Fig. 1) at Step 2 aims at providing an initial clustering of GSs based on the free energy minimization principle. It can be considered as a sequential clustering producing a series of discrete random variables representing cluster numbers. In each different cluster, more GSs are grouped, which should have been generated by the same type of deviation from the original null force hypothesis. Clusters are themselves structured random data that can be useful for a generative model to be learned. The initial clustering process aims at producing a first set of oversegmented clusters, meaning that GSs generated by different local forces should have a low probability of being aggregated, while the false alarm rate for clustering together GSs from different forces should be low. The z_t is processed in sequential order and at each time instant a decision is taken whether to create a new cluster or to join the current GS to the previous cluster by updating it.

Fig. 1: Meta-experience sharing and learning method for a Bayesian autonomous agent. In the situation understanding phase, an agent can start learning from expert demonstrations. These demonstrations are further processed to get noise-free meaningful knowledge as the information passes through the first filtering process. The output of the filtering is a Dynamic Bayesian Network which is an input for a sequential clustering process producing the first model. This model or set of models are situation understandings which the learning agent should map from situation models (SMs) to first-person models (FMs). Observations of the learning agent and the transformed FM models pass through the second filter, that is the agent filtering process. The output of this filtering process passes through another clustering method to get new models and relationships with the previous models. The relations and the new model are then compared to decide about meta-experience fusion. The model comparison step based on the free energy minimization decides to pass either the output as a merging (fused) process or as an addition of a new experience.

Therefore, the sequential unsupervised clustering process can be considered as a sort of discrete filter (or Hidden Markov Model, HMM) where the merging decision is based on free energy minimization. In particular, at time t , the choice of creating a new cluster or updating the previous one is based on how well the fused one could be able to predict the segment of trajectory it represents. This is measured through a set of Kullback–Leibler distances between the trajectory predicted by the model and the sample GSs included in it. For the sake of simplicity, let us assume that the previous cluster contains a single GS. When a new GS is fused to it, the predicted mean speed φ_t is updated by considering the vector between the final point of the new cluster R_t^{max} and the initial point of the previous cluster at time $t - 1$, R_{t-1}^{min} (as this point coincides with the initial position of the new cluster, i.e., $R_t^{min} = R_{t-1}^{min}$), averaged over two cluster samples. A Kalman filter is used to estimate R_t^{max} . The innovation in this filter is then computed as the difference between the new GS final point z_t and its prediction using the previous cluster, i.e., $(R_{t-1}^{max} + \varphi_{t-1})$. The mean value ζ_t , the covariance of the innovation Inn_t ,

the Kalman gain K_t^{Gain} , and the covariance of the fused cluster C_t^R , are computed to update the prediction as well, by considering the new sample following the Kalman filter equation (equation 4). I denotes the identity matrix.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_t &= \Pi z v_t \\
 \zeta_t &= z_t - (R_{t-1}^{max} + \varphi_{t-1}) \\
 Inn_t &= (C_{t-1} + C_t)^{-1} \\
 K_t^{Gain} &= C_{t-1} * Inn_t \\
 R_t^{max} &= R_{t-1}^{max} + \varphi_{t-1} + (K_t^{Gain} * \zeta_t) \\
 C_t^R &= (I - K_t^{Gain}) * C_{t-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The computation of vector φ_t and its covariance allows one to predict other cluster points of the hypothesized fused cluster, starting from the initial coordinates of the first cluster element R_t^{min} . The closer the prediction to GS samples in the cluster, the higher the probability that the fused cluster should be preferred over the creation of a new one. The so computed predicted speed/sample φ_t (indicated using Π)

Fig. 2: Combined models. The new model starts from experience 2 (B) and discovers that using the first experience (A) helps minimize the number of predictors in certain regions, and replaces 7 predictors of B with one predictor of A to complete the route. The ellipses represent a counter level of Gaussian PDFs in a two-dimensional space.

indeed allows one to predict where each progressive sample number k should be, starting from the initial cluster position. However, the estimated final point R_t^{max} changes the attractor direction of the previous cluster, so making the recomputation of errors necessary. As generative clusters define linear prediction domains for the forces they represent, it has to be evaluated whether the fusion of the new GS produces a uniform force field. So, the fused cluster is accepted only if the GSs data can be predicted well from the mean model. Since clusters are assumed to be Gaussian w.r.t. the position and its derivative (composing the GSs), the minimization of the Kullback–Leibler divergence (KLD) error e_t , between predicted positions and samples corresponding to consecutive GS of the fused cluster, can be computed analytically. An upper threshold $THKL = \bar{e} = 2 * mean(e_{1:T})$ is also computed that represents the maximum free energy allowed to perform clustering. We can see the threshold as a KLD value obtained when the distance between the predicted and the reference position is larger than the speed spread in the cluster. If this distance exceeds the threshold, the fusion is not performed and a new cluster is thus created. For instance, still considering the case where a cluster with one element is fused with a new GS at time t , the error e_t is measured as the sum of the errors in intermediate and final points obtained when fusing (noting also that $C_{t-1}^R = C_{t-1}$):

$$e_t = (KLD(R_t^{min} + \varphi_{t-1}, C_{t-1}, R_t^{min} + z v_t, C_t) + KLD(R_t^{min} + 2 * \varphi_{t-1}, C_{t-1}, z x_t + z v_t, C_t)) / 2 \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, when one element is fused into a cluster composed by many elements, the KLD is summed over all cluster points and averaged over the number of samples. In Eq. 5, a second condition on clustering is related to the uncertainty of the speed of the agent in the fused cluster. The speed variance in the direction of motion sv_t , among different GSs in the cluster, has to be lower than 2 times the norm of the velocity φ_t in that cluster, i.e., $THvel = 2 * ||\varphi_t||$. This favors the creation of linear prediction clusters with uniform velocity (small acceleration in direction of motion and quasi uniform spatial sampling of GSs in the direction of the attractor). Creating a new cluster is, therefore, based on the logical-and combination of these thresholds:

$$R_{New} \leftarrow (sv_t \geq THvel) \vee (e_t > THKL) \quad (6)$$

The clustering approach is iterated until no new merging decision is taken. At each step, a new 4D GMM is formed by using estimated clusters. To this end, each cluster is represented by a set of probabilistic parameters describing properties of each Gaussian component, i.e., $(M^{(\tilde{s}_k)E_e}, Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)E_e}, T^{E_e})$. The parameters $M^{(\tilde{s}_k)E_e}$ and $Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)E_e}$ represent the 4D (position and velocity) mean and covariance of the cluster, respectively, in a particular experience E_e . The transition matrix T^{E_e} describes the transition probability between each cluster. Other parameters include the KL error describing how well the cluster components are modeled by the Gaussian.

2) *Second Level Clustering*: The first level clustering is followed by a phase consisting of pruning Gaussian modes

that can be associated with noise (single element clusters), and by a new hierarchical clustering phase aiming at reducing the number of modes. In this phase, a similar KL based minimization merging procedure is applied at a lower adaptive spatial scale. Clusters with small number of elements are merged with adjacent ones when characterized by sufficient alignment, i.e., when they can be predicted by other clusters. The final result, over one experience, is a 4D GMM model that can be represented in the position space showing level curves of Gaussian modes. The mean position of each cluster is at the center of each Gaussian, while the arrow represents the mean speed in that cluster (see for example Fig. 3).

C. SM to FM

The obtained GMM is a generative situational model (SM), i.e., a model in absolute observer coordinates. As this knowledge has to be compared with other experiences in different relative positions in the observed framework, the agent has to use its own first-person (FM) model (see Step 3 in Fig. 1) as a common basis where fusion can be performed. This system can be arbitrarily chosen by fixing the initial position and velocity of the first GS cluster, thus providing a space-invariant domain where it is possible to compare experiences. A GMM FM model can be obtained from an SM one by performing a roto-translation operation applied to all Gaussian modes of the cluster vocabulary (including covariance matrixes). The alignment of different observed experience generative models allows a more straightforward comparison and fusion.

D. Agent Filtering

The agent filtering process (Step 4 in Fig. 1) is a recursive dynamic state estimation that uses a modified version of the filtering method previously described. In this case, the particle filter [21] of the MJPF is modified to use the information of a generative model (as the one represented by GMM clusters obtained at the previous step) to make predictions that are not based on the null force hypothesis but on the information contained in a vocabulary. This way, the agent can estimate its GS vector z_t in a temporal way by doing less work (i.e. with lower free energy), and additionally can measure new relative anomalies at each level of new GS information with respect to previous experiences.

At this stage, the agent has experiences as FM models that can be used as a prior knowledge, and to parametrize predictions. For example, the dynamic model conditioned on the hypothesis of being at time t in a cluster s_t of a certain vocabulary, can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{z}_t = A\tilde{z}_{t-1} + BU_{s_t} + w_t \quad (7)$$

The dynamic model in this last equation allows the agent filtering phase to predict expected states based on the information BU_{s_t} derived from the cluster s_t of the first experience model. Each cluster of the GMM indicates a different spatial region in which the attractors (and so the expected mean speed) are different and determines different control terms BU_{s_t} , by allowing a GMM switching model to adaptively use previous

experiences in trajectory estimation and anomaly detection. Agent filtering can be followed by a clustering step constrained in a similar way, and the result can be converted into FM from SM. Therefore, the agent is capable until now to perform two tasks: 1) obtaining aligned GMM models of multiple experiences; 2) estimating which parts of such experiences at GS level can be predicted from one another and which parts are new (i.e., anomalous with respect to the previous experience generative model).

E. Comparison and Fusion

One experience is a trajectory that is formed by an agent to travel from a starting point P_S to a destination point P_D . Considering the comparative clustering (Step 5 in Fig. 1), the goal is to allow the agent to reduce the number of vocabulary elements required to describe similar experiences by a multimodel filtering procedure that resembles multisensor target tracking methods. In these methods, filtering happens using multiple observations from different sensors. Here the objective of fusion is to build a new GMM model that is updated starting from the first model and using a second GMM model learned from a new experience. The general goal is to minimize the number of modes without losing precision in prediction (when considering the global model). This allows the agent to use more efficiently memory. Moreover, it provides a basic tool to have a minimal set of cluster types, where components of vocabularies adaptively combined can be identified and made more robust by model filtering. This, for example, can be useful for transfer learning to new experiences that are piecewise similar to the ones from which the world model has been learned. The first step is to compare all the clusters of available GMM models with the ones belonging to the new experience model using a KLD distance measure. In the comparison step (see Step 6 in Fig. 1), the best match KL measure (i.e., the cluster that can be better predicted from the first experience) is compared with a KL threshold specific for the cluster statistical characteristics (namely, the component orthogonal to the mean speed of the covariance of the cluster to be updated, and the covariances of the cluster couples) to decide if the update can occur, i.e., if an anomaly is not present. If the free energy is high and an anomaly is present, the new clusters will form a new partial anomaly model. In this paper, we focus on the update steps, while in [5] the authors proposed the extraction and fusion of anomaly models obtained from different experiences. Considering two experience models e_1 and e_2 , a dynamic comparative clustering can be performed to merge non-anomalous clusters.

The comparison step also provides the best match at the cluster element stage, thus identifying the closest points of a unique cluster of the new experience (corresponding to best matched clusters in the model to be updated). Therefore, if in the new experience a single GMM mode is sufficient to reach a point B from A, it is possible to detect when multiple GMM modes (and a more complex transition matrix) are necessary to do the same in the model to be updated. By assuming continuity of GS models, this implies that a subset

(a) Experience one.

(b) Experience two.

Fig. 3: (a) Rectangular movement with collision avoidance. (b) Rectangular trajectory with collision avoidance. The agent learned these two different experiences in a similar region. In this case, the result of fusing them helps the agent to have a concise knowledge. The nested ellipses represent two counter levels of Gaussian PDFs in a two-dimensional space.

Fig. 4: Process based results of fused experiences. As in Fig. 1, here the figure shows the stepwise results. The expert demonstration and new data sequences pass through the filter, thus creating the GS vector sequences. The GS vector sequences are then fed to the clustering algorithm sequentially to create different experiences as situational models. Then, the experiences transformed to the first-person models are again compared and re-clustered as new models. After re-clustering, the entire models will be updated to include the new merged experiences.

of clusters in the model to be updated, starting from a specific element of a cluster to a specific end element of a final cluster, can be simplified by simply replacing them with the more

uniform force field GMM of the new model. This is because the best match validation certifies that cluster elements in the first experience can be predicted using the matching unique

Algorithm 1: Fusion of experiences:

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1 Input:  $M^{(\bar{s}_k)E_1}, Q^{(\bar{s}_k)E_1}, M^{(\bar{s}_k)E_2}, Q^{(\bar{s}_k)E_2}$ 
2 Computation of the table with all the KLD values:
3 for  $k = 1, \dots, K \leftarrow \text{Number of clusters in } e_1$  do
4   for  $g = 1, \dots, G \leftarrow \text{Number of clusters in } e_2$  do
5      $DKL(k, g) =$ 
6        $KLD(M_k^{(\bar{s}_k)E_1}, Q_k^{(\bar{s}_k)E_1}, M_g^{(\bar{s}_k)E_2}, Q_g^{(\bar{s}_k)E_2})$ 
7   end for
8 end for
9 Computation of the colored curves in Fig. 5 (that is, the best match KL
  measure in all time instants from the KLD values)
10 Threshold computation (see black curve in Fig. 5)
11 for  $t = 1, \dots, T \leftarrow \text{All time instants}$  do
12   anomaly computation at  $t$ 
13   find clusters in  $e_2$  one-to-many ( $e_2$  to  $e_1$ ) matching
14   if matching related to "many" is not anomalous then
15     update model replacing the "many" model with "one"
16   else
17     add a new model for both experiences  $e_1$  and  $e_2$  (see [5])
18   end if
19 end for
Output: New and updated models (see Fig.1)
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cluster from the new experience with comparable precision. The threshold and predictability anomaly signals are illustrated in Fig. 5. In this figure, using the discrete time of the new experience as a basis, we can evaluate the distance of the best (minimum) KLD measure (the colors indicate the cluster number). The black line indicates the KL threshold defined for the best matched pair of clusters which the paired GSs belong to. If the KLD measure does not exceed the threshold (associated with the corresponding clusters) this means that in that time we have a more simple model in the new experience that we can use and substitute into the available model, making it more simple without losing precision (as the new GMM well predicts the substituted ones).

The fusion process (see Alg. 1) assumes that an agent is making successive similar experiences and would like to obtain a more simple generative model able to sum up incoming new learned knowledge. The alignment in FM models and the mapping of GMM modes, of both previous and innovation models, are basic aspects to make computation feasible of a distributional-based distance (i.e., KLD) between cluster elements and between clusters. When this distance (i.e., the cross model free energy) is lower than a given threshold, the fusion process creates a new model consisting of a lower number of clusters without losing precision. This process can be again seen as a filter that in this case works on a sequence of models and incrementally updates the agent knowledge when similar experiences (or parts of them) are repeated (Step 7 of Fig. 1).

III. RESULTS

Multiple learned predictive models and new experiences are fused into a single and more robust model with a low number of predictors with comparable precision. Through the principle of free energy minimization, the learned Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks are used to coherently estimate discrete and continuous state variables for hierarchical-level anomaly detection and inference problems, as shown in Fig. 4. This

Fig. 5: KLD anomalies. The black solid line represents the threshold for each data point. The other colors represent cluster based anomaly signals, for each point in the first experience, when it is predicted from the closest element in the second experience.

figure shows the results obtained using a dataset called iCab [22] and synthetic data.

The numbers in the circles in Fig. 4 represent the sequential steps of the learning process from an expert experience or self-experiences in an integrated way. Comparing Fig. 1 with Fig. 4, for conciseness, in the latter we use a single label called filtering, containing both the filtering and agent filtering labels. Similarly, a single clustering label appears in Fig.4, which contains both comparative clustering and clustering.

In our experiment, we obtain 26 predictors in total, when using synthetic data (see Fig. 2). If an agent is intelligent enough, instead of using these models separately, it will combine them to minimize the number of predictors, thus achieving an optimal model with fewer predictors, as shown in Fig. 6(a). On the other hand, Fig. 6(b) shows the final fused model when using the real-world iCab data. The model optimization phase optimizes a set of models which are autobiographical memories as meta-experiences. The fusion process reduces the number of model predictors as the number of experiences increases. In general, new models must have similar or better accuracy, when they are used, compared to previous expert agent experiences. Otherwise, the new models will be saved as particular partial experiences (see [5]), as these models could be anomalies or complete different experiences.

An agent can plan to experience a more optimized solution, by knowing its current state and inferring the next hierarchical-level region information. If two consecutive clusters have similar speed and are parallel in motion, they can be merged, and this indicates that the agent can infer the mean and covariance of its state by using the new cluster, enhancing predictability. To minimize over-segmentation in the proposed sequential clustering, the aggregation of similar curvatures in the sequential clusters should be expected. This is important for an agent to enhance its intelligence in performing new tasks without explicitly learning them. In other words, the agent

(a) Merged experience with 10 predictors (synthetic dataset).

(b) Merged experience with 15 predictors (iCab dataset).

Fig. 6: (a) Merged experience (see also Fig. 2) considering the synthetic dataset with a new model having 10 predictors. (b) Merged experiences considering the real iCab dataset having 15 predictors.

(a) Predicted trajectories w.r.t. the ground truth (GT).

(b) MSE between predicted and updated GSs.

Fig. 7: (a) Predicted trajectories w.r.t. the ground truth in a continuous blue line. Red stands for GNG, green for SEQ. The same number of clusters is used in both algorithms. (b) MSE between predicted and updated GSs. Here, brown stands for SEQ, light blue for GNG. A different number of clusters is now used.

can perform more tasks in an exploration way. The merging process does not replace the previous experiences, but allows the agent to perform a new more optimized experience, as shown in Fig. 6. For re-usability purposes, the new experience will be added in the autobiographical memory of an agent.

Table I shows the comparison results for different anomaly measures using the GNG clustering method. This is a method commonly used in recent papers proposed in literature [23]–[26]. The errors are related to super-state (SS) and state (S) level anomalies (such as CLA and CLB [27]), as well as the inference (prediction vs. observation) anomaly computed in terms of MSE. Overall, we can note that the fused vocabulary

enables the agent to achieve comparable results with state-of-the-art methods, by using a low number of clusters. One advantage of using the merged experience is mainly in reducing the number of predictors. As an example, the number of predictors in GNG is 36 while in our method is 15, when considering the iCab dataset.

Furthermore, Fig. 7(a) shows the predicted trajectories, including the ground truth, when considering both the GNG and SEQ clustering algorithms (using the same number of clusters). We can notice that our algorithm performs well, allowing us to obtain a final model with better prediction results. On the other hand, in Fig. 7(b), we show the MSE

TABLE I: Quantitative analysis of the proposed method based on different anomaly measures (a different number of clusters is used).

Anomaly measures	S _{CLA}	S _{CLB}	SS _{KLD}	MSE
GNG based Clu	3.2065	6.7510	26.4369	0.6764
SEQ based Clu	1.0681	22.7764	41.7745	0.7071

signal between the prediction and update level messages of the GSs, when the number of clusters in the GNG clustering is higher than SEQ. In this case, the GNG exhibits better prediction results, but the number of predictors in the GNG is greater than SEQ, while maintaining comparable precision between the two algorithms.

IV. CONCLUSION

It is possible to flexibly combine models that are learned for particular tasks and that can be then transferred to do similar tasks with simple modifications in a generative manner. The experience merging process can start by considering a low number of experiences (e.g., two experiences as done in this work) and can carry on by generating different models, which can also be applied in unknown situations (or environments). If an agent has fewer models in its autobiographical memory, the fusion process will be easier as the number of computations to derive the KLD distances depends on the number of clusters. Moreover, in a potential future work where we could fuse different sensor data, improving the predictability of the model that uses low-dimensional sensor inputs, could help the agent learn high-dimensional sensor inputs in a guided way.

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